

The Effect of Training and Emotional Intelligence on Intrinsic Motivation-Mediated Competence (Case Study: Teacher of SLBN 1 Bengkulu City)

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Abstract:- Teachers who teach in extraordinary schools have a teaching role in achieving the expected educational goals, are required to be able to understand differences in personality characters in children with different special needs, such as differences in the ability to understand lessons, the ability to control emotions, especially in hyperactive children and the ability to establish relationships with friends around them. So in this study, the approach taken is the Effect of Training, and Emotional Intelligence on Intrinsic Motivation-Mediated Competencies in SLBN 01 Teachers in Bengkulu City" The research method used is Causal Quantitative. The population of this study was teachers of SLBN 01 Bengkulu City with a sample of 90 teachers. This study uses SEM PLS data analysis where the data processing uses the SmartPLS 3.0 application. This research proves that the direct influence is that Training has a positive and significant effect on Competence, Emotional Intelligence has a positive and significant effect on Competence, Intrinsic Motivation has a positive and significant effect on Competence, Training has a positive and significant effect on Intrinsic Motivation, Emotional Intelligence has a positive and significant effect on Intrinsic Motivation. Then this study proves the indirect influence that Training has a positive and significant effect on intrinsic motivation through competence and Emotional Intelligence has a positive and significant effect on intrinsic motivation through competence.

Keywords:- Training, Emotional Intelligence, Competence, Intrinsic Motivationk.

I. INTRODUCTION

Education plays an important role in human life. Education is one of the basic needs needed by humans for survival. The world of education always experiences development every time. As time progresses, so does the number of population.

According to Fasli Jalal as Head of the National Population and Family Planning Agency (BKKBN) said that children with special needs are children who experience dysfunction physically, mentally / intellectually, socially, and emotionally

Teachers who teach in extraordinary schools have a teaching role in achieving the expected educational goals, are required to be able to understand differences in personality characters in children with different needs

In the Government Regulation of the Republic of Indonesia no. 19 of 2005 concerning National Education Standards Chapter VI part one concerning Teachers article 28 paragraph (1) which reads: "Teachers must have academic qualifications and competencies as learning agents, be physically and mentally healthy, and have the ability to realize the goals of national education, paragraph (2) which reads: "Competencies as learning agents at the primary and secondary education levels and early childhood education include: pedagogic competence, personality competence, professional competence and social competence. Sekolah Luar Luar (SLB) Negeri 1 Kota Bengkulu is an educational institution for children with special needs, those who have special needs permanently / disability and temporarily so that they need adjustments to educational services.

Researchers have conducted an initial study in October 2022, namely by making observations to collect some data – data on the number of students in BPS (Bada Statistics Center) Bengkulu City.

Fig 1 Number of SLB Students in Bengkulu Province by Education Level

Based on data from BPS Bengkulu Province, the number of children with special needs recorded as studying in special schools (SLB) reached 998 students in the 2019/2020 school year. Of these, there are 354 ABK at the elementary education level, as many as 476 ABK at the junior high school level and 539 ABK at the high school level. In the 2020/2021 school year, it reached 1,203.

The Ministry of Education and Culture (Kemendikbud) estimates that almost 70% of children with special needs do not receive proper education. The latest data from the Central Statistics Agency (BPS) 2021 states that the number of children with special needs (ABK) in Indonesia is that more than 1 million children with special needs have not received education that is important for their lives. Sekolah Luar Luar (SLB) Negeri 1 Kota Bengkulu is an educational institution for children with special needs, those who have special needs permanently / disability and temporarily so that they need adjustments to educational services.

Based on the results of the pre-survey regarding the factors that affect the lack of optimal competence, it is stated in statement number 3, namely "training that has been followed" with a respondent's choice value of 24 (89%).

The pre-survey results are in line with research conducted by Tsani *et. al.*, (2020) The results obtained in the study showed that training and competency variables had a positive and significant effect on motivation. With some problems that still occur in SLBN 01 Bengkulu City, it should be an important concern in order to advance the organization by encouraging and developing human resources to have higher competence in the organization.

II. THEORETICAL FOUNDATION

A. Competence-based View Concept

The term and concept of competency introduced by David McClelland in his article on "Testing for Competence Rather Than Intelligence" explains that competence is a fundamental (and hidden) characteristic of a person who has a causal relationship (causation) to provide superior / special / effective performance according to criteria set in advance, in a particular job or situation. Michael Zwell (in Ayuningrum, 2010) revealed that there are several factors that can affect a person's competency skills, which are as follows:

- *Beliefs and Values*
- *Skills*
- *Experience*
- *Personality Characteristics*
- *Motivation*
- *Emotional issues*
- *Intellectual ability*
- *Organizational culture*

B. Training

According to Dessler in Katidjan *et al.*, (2018), training is a learning process necessary for employees to do their jobs.

➤ *According to Simamora (2006), there are Various Tangible benefits obtained from Training and Development Programs, Including:*

- *Increase the quantity and quality of productivity*
- *Reduce the learning time required by employees to achieve accepted performance standards*
- *Forming attitudes, loyalty and cooperation that are more beneficial*
- *Meet human resource planning needs*
- *Reduce the frequency and cost of work accidents*
- *Assist employees in personal improvement and development*

Factors that support the success of training according to Veithzal Rivai (2011) are: Material., Methods., Facilities or principles of learning Trainees, Evaluation. Training There are many factors that determine the success of a training program.

C. Emotional Intelligence

According to Goleman (2009), emotional intelligence is the ability to motivate oneself and endure frustration, control impulses and not exaggerate pleasure, regulate mood and keep the burden of stress from paralyzing the ability to think, empathize and pray. Goleman (2015).

Dimensions and Indicators of Emotional Intelligence According to Goleman (2015) the component of emotional intelligence or emotional skills framework has five dimensions, namely:

➤ *Self-Awareness*

Basically dimensions to know one's own condition, preferences, resources and institutions, such as: emotional awareness. With the indicators:

- *Improvement in recognizing and feeling one's own emotions*
- *Better able to understand the causes of Feelings that arise*

• *With the Indicators:*

- ✓ *Improvement in recognizing and feeling one's own emotions*
- ✓ *Better able to understand the causes of Feelings that arise*

➤ *Self-Regulation*

Putting pressure on self-managing conditions, impulses, and resources, such as: self-control, trustworthiness, alertness, adaptability, and innovation. By its indicators: Higher tolerance for frustration and anger management

- *Better Handling of Mental Tension*

➤ *Motivation*

Namely emotional tendencies that usher in or facilitate the transition of goals, such as: encouragement of achievement, commitment, initiative and optimism. With the indicators:

- *More Responsible*
- *Able to focus on the task at hand*
- *More self-control*

➤ *Empathy*

It is an awareness of the feelings, needs, and interests of others, a service orientation, developing others such as: understanding others, a service orientation, developing others, overcoming diversity and political awareness. With the indicators:

- *More able to accept other people's points of view*
- *Improve empathy and sensitivity to the feelings of others*

➤ *Social Skills*

It is a skill of managing the emotions of others, maintaining relationships with others through social skills, leadership and successful interpersonal relationships. With the indicators:

- *Better in Solving Problems that Arise.*
- *Can Share Feelings, Cooperate and Like to Help*

➤ *Theoretical Framework*

After the presentation of the hypothesis development for this study, the conceptual framework for this study is as follows:

Fig 2 Conceptual Framework

➤ *The Hypotheses in this Study are as follows:*

- *H1: There is a positive and significant influence of Training on Competency.*
- *H2: There is a positive and significant influence of Emotional Intelligence on Competence.*
- *H3: There is a positive and significant influence of Intrinsic Motivation on Competence.*
- *H4: There is a positive and significant effect of training on intrinsic motivation*

- *H5: There is a positive and significant influence of emotional intelligence on intrinsic motivation*
- *H6: There is a positive and significant influence of Training in mediating Intrinsic Motivation on Competency*
- *H7: There is a positive and significant influence of Emotional Intelligence in mediating Intrinsic Motivation on Competence*

III. RESEARCH METHODS

This study used a quantitative approach of exploratory studies that often rely on secondary research (such as literature reviews).

The design carried out in this study is a causality research design.

The population in this study was 90 teachers.

In this study the sample used was permanent teachers from all levels of teachers totaling 90 people non probability sampling with saturated samples. The data collection method is carried out by distributing questionnaires to respondents using the Ordinal scale, according to (Sugiyono, 2018) The Ordinal scale is a measurement scale that not only states the category but also states the rank construct being measured.

Researchers use quantitative descriptive methods based on the purpose of this study, which is to test hypotheses whose empirical models have more than one dependent variable. Researchers use SEM-PLS, which is a variant-based structural equation model (SEM) or partial least square (PLS) to evaluate hypotheses.

IV. RESEARCH RESULTS

From the 90 respondents, there were 40 respondents or 45.2% were male-laki. While the remaining 50 respondents or 54.9% were female.

In this study 11 respondents or 13.2% of the total respondents had ages ranging from < 25 years, 25 - 30 years there were 38 or 41.1% then aged 30 - 40 years there were 22 or 28.3% and the rest >40 years there were 19 or 17.4%. In answering this questionnaire, there were 5 respondents or 7.3%, then the Diploma (D3) education level there were 15 respondents or 18.2%, the S1 Bachelor education level there were 45 respondents or 45.4%, and the S2 Bachelor education level there were 25 respondents or 29.1%.

A. Data Quality Test Results

➤ Modified Results of Convergent Validity Testing

The modified results of *convergent validity* testing with confirmatory factor analysis show indicators with a *standardized loading factor value* of > 0.50.

- *PLS Algorithm Results*

Fig 3 Convergent Validity

Convergent validity testing in the figure above can be seen that all indicators have met convergent validity because they have a loading factor value above 0.50.

- *Composite Reliability Test Results*

Table 1 Composite Reliability Test Results

Variable	Composite Reliability	Information
Training	0.949	Very High Reliability
Emotional Intelligence	0.916	Very High Reliability
Intrinsic Motivation	0.892	High Reliability
Competence	0.929	Very High Reliability

The results of the composite reliability graph test have a value of ≥ 0.7 , it means that the construct has good reliability or the questionnaire used as a tool in this study has been reliable or consistent.

- *Cronbach's Alpha Test Results*

Table 2 Cronbach's Alpha Test Results

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	Information
Training	0.942	Very High Reliability
Emotional Intelligence	0.897	High Reliability
Intrinsic Motivation	0.862	High Reliability
Competence	0.918	Very High Reliability

From the test results cronbach's alpha shows a satisfactory value, because all latent variables have a value of cronbach's alpha ≥ 0.70 . This means that all latent variables are said to be reliable.

- *Results of hypothesis testing (estimation of path coefficients)*

See the significance of the hypothesis by looking at the value of the parameter coefficient and the significance value of T-statistics in the bootstrapping report algorithm. To find out significant or insignificant seen from the T-table at alpha 0.05 (5%) = 1.96, then the T-table is compared with the T-count (T-statistic). Then Specific Indirect Effects (Mediation Effect) How to interpret Specific indirect effects bootstrapping PLS SEM results is not much different from the interpretation of direct effects bootstrapping PLS SEM.

Table 3 Results of Testing the *Dirrect Effect* Hypothesis (Direct Effect)

Variable	Original Sample	Sample Mean	Standard Deviation	T. Statistic	P Values	Significance
Competency > Training	0.256	0.270	0.130	1.976	0.049	Significant Positive
Emotional Intelligence -> Competencies	0.220	0.222	0.102	2.144	0.033	Significant Positive
Intrinsic Motivation -> Competence	0.451	0.441	0.139	3.237	0.001	Significant Positive
Training -> Intrinsic Motivation	0.536	0.528	0.068	7.901	0.000	Significant Positive
Emotional Intelligence -> Intrinsic Motivation	0.451	0.466	0.074	6.138	0.000	Significant Positive
<i>INDIRECT INFLUENCE</i>						
Variable	Original Sample	Sample Mean	Standard Deviation	T. Statistic	P Values	Significance
Training -> Intrinsic Motivation -> Competency	0.242	0.233	0.082	2.958	0.003	Significant Positive
Emotional Intelligence -> Intrinsic Motivation -> Competence	0.204	0.205	0.073	2.803	0.005	Significant Positive

- *Based on the Above, it can be Concluded that the Results of Hypothesis Testing in this Study there are five Accepted Hypotheses*
- ✓ Hypothesis 1 on training variables has a positive and significant effect on competence.
- ✓ Hypothesis 2 on emotional intelligence variables has a positive and significant effect on competence.
- ✓ Hypothesis 3 on intrinsic motivation variables has a positive and significant effect on competence.
- ✓ Hypothesis 4 on training variables has a positive and significant effect on intrinsic motivation.
- ✓ Hypothesis 5 on emotional intelligence variables has a positive and significant effect on intrinsic motivation.
- ✓ Then the results of indirect influence on training variables are positive and significant in mediating the influence of intrinsic motivation on competence. Furthermore, the results of indirect influence on emotional intelligence variables are positive and significant in mediating the influence of intrinsic motivation on competence.

V. DISCUSSION

➤ *The Effect of Training on Competency*

Based on the results of the first hypothesis test in this study, it shows that training has a significant positive effect on competence. Training materials are an important element in implementing training programs. The content of the program is determined by the identification of training needs and objectives. Programs may seek to teach specific skills, impart needed knowledge or change attitudes. The better the training provided by the management to SLBN 01 Bengkulu City Teachers, the higher the competence of SLBN 01 Bengkulu City Teachers.

Studies related to the most dominant measurement, namely material, training materials can be: Management (management), mastery of manuscripts, work psychology, work communication, work discipline and ethics, work management and reporting. In this case, the method used must use participatory techniques, where participants also participate and play an active role in these educational activities. For example, group discussions, conferences, simulations, role plays (demonstrations) and games. Exercises, exams, group work and study visits (comparative studies).

The results of this study are in line with research conducted by Handojo et al., (2022) the effect of ISM code training and cadet learning motivation on the competence of stimaryo cadets whose results show that ISM Code training and cadet learning motivation have a positive and significant effect on cadet competence. ISM Code training and cadet learning motivation are able to explain cadet competencies. Furthermore, Nehemiah, Mafizatun (2021) Training has a positive effect on teacher competence. The need for achievement positively affects teacher performance through mediating variables of teacher competence. Training positively affects teacher performance through teacher competency variables.

➤ *The Effect of Emotional Intelligence on Competency*

Based on the results of the second hypothesis test in this study shows that emotional intelligence has a significant positive effect on competence. Because with a good understanding of emotional intelligence can improve competence, it is proven by the results of the study above shows that emotional intelligence has a positive and significant effect on the competence of SLBN 01 Bengkulu City Teachers.

Studies related to the most dominant measurement, namely self-awareness. Self-awareness is a person's ability to recognize their own feelings and those of others, as well as their own strengths and weaknesses. Emotional intelligence also encourages a person to show his honesty. People with good emotional intelligence are able to think clearly under pressure, act ethically, follow principles, and achieve their desires. Emotional intelligence means using emotions effectively to achieve goals correctly and build productive and successful working relationships at work.

The results of this study are in line with research conducted by Barbara et al., (2021) revealed that emotional intelligence directly and positively predicts all variables of relationship needs satisfaction, and indirectly predicts greater intrinsic motivation through student-focused relationship needs satisfaction. According to Darman, et al., (2021) The results showed that intellectual intelligence variables had a positive and significant effect on employee competence and performance

➤ *The Effect of Intrinsic Motivation on Competency*

Based on the results of the third hypothesis test in this study shows that intrinsic motivation has a significant positive effect on competence. By always cultivating intrinsic motivation, it will be able to increase competence. Therefore, stimulants to increase intrinsic motivation must be arranged through planned and programmed stages of activity so that employees have intrinsic motivation that is always high which will later have an impact on competence. The better the motivation given by the management to SLBN 01 Bengkulu City Teachers, the higher the competence of SLBN 01 Bengkulu City Teachers.

Studies are related to the most dominant measurement, namely the work itself. Basically, people have different motivations depending on the number of thoughts, such as personality, ambition, education and age. An important driver that makes people work is the need that must be met, both conscious and unconscious, both tangible and intangible, as well as physical and mental needs that stimulate work ethic so that employees work more seriously. It can really provide more support to achieve organizational goals. Work motivation shows not only based on the value of money received (monthly value), because if a person's basic needs (for living) can be met, then he needs things that satisfy his soul (love), such as work. Satisfaction, appreciation, respect, working atmosphere and things that satisfy their desire to develop (learn), that is, the opportunity to work and develop themselves. So that finally people work or do something because of values, namely wanting to have

a more meaningful life and be able to leave something to their loved ones (to leave a legacy).

The results of this study are in line with research conducted by Barat, et al., (2021) in the title of the study Improving Teacher Performance with Competence through Job Satisfaction and Intrinsic Motivation as Intervening Variables (Study at State Vocational Schools in Serang City) whose results of this study state that intrinsic motivation affects competence in a partial mediation manner. Suzan et. al., (2021) work motivation has a positive and significant effect on improving teacher competence at private school "AAA" in Makassar City; (2) Job training has a negative and insignificant effect on improving teacher competence at "AAA" private schools in Makassar City.

➤ *The effect of training on intrinsic motivation*

Based on the results of the fourth hypothesis test in this study shows that training has a significant positive effect on intrinsic motivation. The training provided by the management is directly beneficial for teachers so that it has a positive and significant impact on intrinsic motivation. The better the training provided by the management to SLBN 01 Bengkulu City Teachers, the higher the intrinsic motivation that exists in SLBN 01 Bengkulu City Teachers.

Many education professionals have now developed innovative learning methods. The effectiveness of the application of these learning methods to improve the quality of learning has also been empirically proven in various studies. With this learning method, it attracts and encourages students to dive directly into the learning process and train all students to work together, so that students are expected to actively participate in the learning process. So that the use of this learning method can increase motivation and ultimately achieve learning outcomes that are in accordance with the perfection of school learning.

The results of this study are in line with research conducted by Meidia (2019) The results of this study show that training has a significant effect on work motivation, competence has a significant effect on work motivation According to research conducted by Naizm (2021) Does Intrinsic Motivation Mediate the Impact of Employee Training on Employee Creativity? Task Complexity moderation model. All three hypotheses are accepted and supported by significant findings from existing researchers. These findings help conclude that employee training if nurtured in Pakistan's corporate sector will significantly ease employee creativity in the work environment. Useful profits can then be achieved by increasing employee creativity which will indirectly benefit the company itself.

➤ *The Effect of Emotional Intelligence on Intrinsic Motivation*

Based on the results of the fifth hypothesis test in this study shows that emotional intelligence has a significant positive effect on intrinsic motivation. Emotional intelligence is a person's ability to monitor and control his own feelings and others, and use those feelings to guide more positive thoughts and actions, where a person will

have a tendency to strive for success in achieving learning goals at SLBN 01 Bengkulu City Teachers.

Studies related to the most dominant measurement, namely self-regulation. Self-regulation is the ability to control one's emotions. The better the self-regulation of emotions, the more controlled the actions taken, so that good relationships with others remain established. The concept of emotional intelligence thus refers to self-awareness that allows people to recognize emotions and control and manage their own. Many studies show that emotional intelligence is essential to successfully achieve one's goals. Because people who are able to manage and manage their emotional intelligence can survive and be accepted in any work environment because they can control their emotions and invest themselves in the organization.

The results of this study are in line with research conducted by Fajri, et al., (2021) in the research title The Relationship of Emotional Intelligence and Parental Behavior to Entrepreneurial Motivation in Unsyiah Final Students, the results of this study stated that emotional intelligence and parental behavior had an effective impact of 18.8% on student entrepreneurial motivation. Then according to Alkiyumi (2021) The results of this study also show that there is no mediating role of emotional intelligence in predicting intrinsic motivation in the ability to solve mathematical problems.

➤ *Effect of Training -> Intrinsic Motivation -> Competency*

Training is influential in mediating the influence of intrinsic motivation on competence. It can be concluded that the accepted hypothesis that training has a significant positive effect on intrinsic motivation through competence shows statistical significance.

Studies related to the most dominant measurement are methods that require appropriate methods for each organization that organizes training, so that the content of training can be easily assimilated by employees who attend training. The purpose of this training program is to improve job performance and reduce employee turnover in order to carry out work better.

From the results of this study, it shows that to improve the competence of SLBN 01 Bengkulu City teachers is not enough just to attend training, but which also requires high intrinsic motivation in order to improve competence. This emphasizes that efforts to improve the competence of SLBN 01 Bengkulu City teachers are very dependent on how well the training is followed by the teacher and the intrinsic motivation that the teacher has. The results of this study are in line with research conducted by Idrus (2019) whose research results of training and motivation together have a positive and significant effect on competence.

➤ *Influence of Emotional Intelligence -> Intrinsic Motivation -> Competence*

Emotional intelligence is influential in mediating the influence of intrinsic motivation on competence. It can be concluded that the accepted hypothesis that emotional intelligence has a significant positive effect on intrinsic motivation through competence. This shows statistical significance.

Studies related to the most dominant measurement is motivation, motivation is the drive that encourages employees to achieve maximum goals. Motivation is a process of continuous effort that comes from promoting something that is considered important to him.

The results of this study show that to improve the competence of SLBN 01 Bengkulu City teachers is not enough only to understand emotional intelligence but also requires high intrinsic motivation in order to improve competence. This emphasizes that efforts to improve the competence of SLBN 01 Bengkulu City teachers depend on how well they can understand the emotional intelligence and intrinsic motivation of the teacher. The results of this study are in line with research conducted by Santika, et al., (2019) the results of his research explain that emotional intelligence contributes to the competence of students' social studies knowledge. and interest in learning contributes to the competence of students' social studies knowledge. Furthermore, emotional intelligence and learning motivation simultaneously affect the competence of social studies knowledge. Marlina, et al., (2018) the results of her research on work motivation were also found to significantly mediate the influence of emotional intelligence and competence on employee performance. Therefore, to further improve the performance of government apparatus, work motivation must be increased through increased emotional intelligence and competence.

VI. CONCLUSION AND ADVICE

A. Conclusion

- Training has a significant positive effect on competence, with the material dimension having the strongest influence.
 - Emotional intelligence has a significant positive effect on competence, with the dimension of self-awareness being the most powerful.
 - Intrinsic motivation has a significant positive effect on competence, with the dimension of the job itself, the most powerful.
 - Training has a significant positive effect on intrinsic motivation, with the method dimension having the strongest effect.
 - Emotional intelligence has a significant positive effect on intrinsic motivation, with the dimension of self-regulation being the most powerful.
 - Training is influential in mediating the influence of intrinsic motivation on competence, with the dimension of the method having the strongest influence.
- Emotional intelligence is influential in mediating the influence of intrinsic motivation on competence, with the motivational dimension being the most powerful.

B. Advice

➤ *Advice for Teachers of SLBN 01 Bengkulu City*

Based on the results of research, discussion, and conclusions, researchers can provide suggestions or input to SLBN 01 Bengkulu City Teachers. and subsequent researchers, among others:

- In the training variable, it was found that the largest and significant material dimensions affected competence. In this case, schools should use trainers from outside or trainers who are qualified in their fields so that the training program can be maximized and is expected to produce reliable and qualified personnel/teachers in their fields/workplaces with good performance, thus supporting achievement.
- In the emotional intelligence variable, it was found that the dimension of self-awareness was the largest and significantly influenced competence. To increase company productivity, it is necessary to increase employee awareness of the balance of emotional intelligence by training qualified employees.
- In the intrinsic motivation variable, it was found that the dimension of the work itself, most significantly and significantly influenced competence. This is so that employees can complete their work correctly. As a solution, companies need ways to increase feelings to help other employees with activities or events outside of school and working hours, such as leisure activities, holidays for all employees and also 5S (polite, generous smiles, greetings and condolences).
- In the training variable, the method dimension was found, the largest and most significant influence on intrinsic motivation. In this case, students with intellectual disabilities use adaptive methods where the application consists of communicating several times until they understand and really understand what is being communicated. Students are guided individually so that student progress is visible and teachers can find out what difficulties students experience in following learning. For students with disabilities, teachers use lecture and practice methods, but these methods do not make the material delivered can be understood optimally by students, but appropriate methods are still needed. Students who need special support have different learning barriers, such as: who have difficulty understanding what the teacher is teaching. This is because their thinking ability is weak. Facing these obstacles, adaptive methods are a good way to provide understanding to them, because the material delivered by teachers and the difficulty of people with disabilities move optimally with these obstacles, teachers should avoid material that requires maximum movement.
- In the emotional intelligence variable, it was found that the dimension of self-regulation, most significantly and significantly influenced intrinsic motivation. Managing emotions in order to be expressed appropriately is a

skill that depends on self-regulation. Emotional intelligence includes different, but complementary, abilities of academic intelligence, that is, purely cognitive abilities as measured by IQ.

- In the training variable, the method dimension was found, the largest and significant influence in mediating the influence of intrinsic motivation on competence. In this case Methods, media and training plans that must be adapted to the needs of employees to support their work, in addition to the proposals and infrastructure that the company provides for this. Training can run optimally. Thus increasing the morale, motivation and work ability of employees. In addition, it can also conduct regular exercises with this type (In-house training) for employees with specific skills in a particular field and have a lot of experience in a particular field so that they can share their knowledge and experience with other employee participants. Not only that, employees can also get public training attended by employees. Various kinds of seminars, workshops in accordance with the field of knowledge to be obtained
- In the emotional intelligence variable, the dimension of motivation was found, the largest and significant influence in mediating the influence of intrinsic motivation on competence. The need to provide encouragement and motivation for employees to be more active in work

➤ *Advice for Next Researchers*

Advice for future researchers, preferably those who will conduct research in the same field and use this thesis as a reference, then it needs to be reviewed again because it does not rule out the possibility of statements that are not appropriate, because the author feels there are still many shortcomings and limitations in completing this thesis. So that further research can be carried out on SLBN 01 Teachers in Bengkulu City. others by replacing different research models or conducting research on different types of objects and expanding the research sample with different types of variables such as: Principal Leadership, School Climate, Cooperation, Teacher Performance, and Job Satisfaction in order to be comparative and increase the scope of broader generalizations.

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